

Efficiency of financing environmental protection measures in the context of Ukraine's future membership in the EU

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Abstract: Over the past decades, humanity has had a significant negative impact on the environment. This problem can be solved only by establishing a rational environmental management policy and ensuring an effective financial policy in the context of balancing emissions and expenditures on environmental protection measures. The purpose of the article is to analyze the efficiency of financing environmental protection measures by determining the dependence of pollutant emissions on environmental protection expenditures in Ukraine and the European Union. The study identified the dynamics of revenues from environmental taxes in Ukraine: taxes on air emissions prevail. Most of the expenditures are made from the state budget. According to the functional classification, environmental expenditures are mainly aimed at preventing and eliminating environmental pollution. To assess the effectiveness of the state policy in the field of environmental protection, we analyzed the dependence of pollutant emissions in Ukraine, Poland and Romania on the amount of environmental expenditures, investments in this area and revenues from environmental tax. In Ukraine, the amount of pollutants released into the atmosphere depends most of all on investments in this area, in Poland - on revenues from environmental taxes, and in Romania - on expenditures on environmental protection. It has been established that the obtained models are adequate and can be used to build future forecasts of pollutant emissions. Directions for the development of financial and environmental policy are proposed.

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1. Introduction

Globalization has a significant impact on people's lifestyles [1]. It is transforming socio-economic forms of development within the existing natural resource and environmental conditions [2]. Globalization increases communication, accelerates access to technology and innovation, and it has ushered in an era of economic prosperity [1]. On the other hand, all of this has a negative impact on the environment and is a significant problem of the 21st century [3], which provokes climate change, droughts, fires, etc. [4]. Environmental protection, rational use of resources, and ensuring ecological protection of human life are prerequisites for sustainable economic and social development of any

country [5]. Ensuring ecological safety, namely the protection and restoration of the environment, is a priority task of the state and society [6]. One of the important areas of this sector is the alignment of financial flows with a sustainable way to achieve long-term climate and development goals [7]. The main directions of modern socio-environmental policy are the greening of social production and ensuring the environmental safety of the population and natural ecosystems [8]. The solution of environmental problems largely depends on the efficiency of the financial support system, the established composition and volume of funding sources, and the identified priority areas of their use, which requires a scientifically based analysis [9]. In Ukraine, the main sources of public funding for environmental protection are currently the state and local budgets [1]. In the structure of environmental financing, the key place is occupied by environmental taxes and fees, the proceeds from which are used to protect the environment, minimize the negative impact of economic activity and rational use of natural resources [10]. At the same time, the current system of regulation in the field of environmental management and environmental taxation in Ukraine, the existing level of payments and fees are not able to ensure sustainable development of progress in the accumulation of financial resources and targeted allocation of funds for environmental activities [11]. Therefore, the implementation of successful foreign experience in this area to the Ukrainian economic space can yield positive results at the initial stages of reform [12].

The purpose of the article is to analyze the efficiency of financing environmental protection measures by determining the dependence of pollutant emissions on environmental protection expenditures in Ukraine and the European Union.

2. Materials and Methods

The main research period is 2015-2021 inclusive. This time period allows us to form an objective vision of the situation, since until 2014, the statistics contained information on the temporarily occupied territories, and in 2022, due to the beginning of the full-scale invasion, environmental protection expenditures decreased significantly due to objective factors and do not contain information on the territories temporarily occupied after February 24, 2022. To understand the scale of the problem that currently exists in Ukraine, we have additionally displayed some indicators for 2022 and calculated projected indicators for 2023.

To form a statistical sample for the correlation and regression model, the time interval 2015-2020 was chosen. Time periods before 2015 were not analyzed, as they contain somewhat outdated information and are incomparable due to the beginning of Russian aggression. Information about 2021 is not available in the statistics, and the figures for 2022 are incomparable due to the beginning of Russia's full-scale invasion, which affected environmental policy as well. Therefore, it is illogical to use such data to determine certain patterns under optimal sustainable conditions. Therefore, the model is based on data for 2015-2020.

The statistical information is systematized on the basis of open data from the Open budget web portal, the State Statistics Service, and Eurostat.

The following methods were used for the study: analysis, synthesis, generalization, comparison, specification, statistical and graphical methods.

Using the correlation and regression analysis, the influence of factors on the emissions of major pollutants into the atmosphere was assessed. Emissions of the main pollutants into the atmosphere are defined as the resultant feature. Expenditures and investments and environmental tax revenues were chosen as factor attributes. At the first stage, correlation matrices were constructed using the Microsoft Excel data block "Data Analysis" (Correlation tool), which determine the correlation between the dependent and independent variables. Based on the results of the correlation analysis, the data for regression analysis were selected. Then, based on the formed sample, a regression analysis was conducted, which shows the contribution of the independent variable to the variation of the dependent variable under study. This analysis was conducted using the Microsoft Excel data block "Data Analysis" (the "Regression" tool). At the final stage, based on the built linear regression equation, the predicted values of pollutant emissions were calculated.

3. Results

Tax policy is a part of the government's toolkit used to address environmental issues, including climate change. Environmental taxation can help reduce environmentally harmful behavior while generating revenue at all levels of government [13]. The national legislation emphasizes that the main purpose of establishing an environmental tax is to increase incentives for the rational use of natural resources [14].

In Ukraine, environmental taxes include:

- an environmental tax levied on emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere by stationary sources of pollution (except for emissions of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere);
- revenues from pollutant disposals directly into water bodies;
- revenues from waste disposal in specially designated places or facilities, except for disposal of certain types of waste as secondary raw materials;
- environmental tax levied on the generation of radioactive waste (including already accumulated waste) and/or temporary storage of radioactive waste by its producers beyond the period established by the special conditions of licenses;
- an environmental tax levied on carbon dioxide emissions from stationary sources of pollution (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Revenues from environmental taxes (according to the consolidated budget of Ukraine, UAH million).

Source: based on data from [15].

As can be seen from Fig. 1, taxes on air emissions account for the largest share of the total amount of environmental taxes. In total, in 2015-2023, including taxes on carbon dioxide emissions, they amount to 44.1%, 62.8%, 54.5%, 52.5%, 43.7%, 37.6%, 39.3%, 28.7%, and 25.1%, respectively. The share of taxes on emissions into water bodies ranged from 5% in 2015-2022 and is projected to reach 9.2% in 2023. The maximum share of revenues from the disposal of waste in specially designated places during 2015-2022 was 25.4% in 2015, and the minimum share was 12.5% (projected) in 2023.

The share of the environmental tax levied for the generation and/or storage of radioactive waste in the total amount of environmental taxes in 2015-2021 averaged 19.1%. From 2020 to 2023, the share is projected to decrease by 5.6%.

The share of the environmental tax levied on carbon dioxide emissions from stationary sources of pollution increased by 24.3% in 2019-2023.

The share of the environmental tax on carbon dioxide emissions increased from 15.6% to 39.9% in 2019-2023.

Revenues from the environmental tax on air emissions, excluding carbon dioxide, increased significantly in 2016 compared to 2015 (+164.2%), then the amount of funds decreased by 18.2% and remained almost unchanged in 2018-2019. In 2020, compared to 2019, there was a decline of 25.5%, followed by an increase of 22.8% and a further significant chain reduction of 42.3%. In 2023, the decrease in revenues is projected at 17.6%.

In 2016-2018 and in 2021, there was an increase in revenues from discharges into water bodies by 27.3%, 1.8%, 9.8% and 7.1% compared to the previous year, respectively. A decrease in revenues occurred in 2019-2020 (-2.1% and -4.9%, respectively). In 2022, there was a sharp increase compared to 2021 (+42.4%). Growth is also predicted for 2023 (+88.1%).

In 2015-2019, the total increase in revenues from waste disposal in designated areas was 67.5%. During 2019-2022, their value changed in waves: in 2019 and 2021, there was an increase (+8.7% and 15.7%, respectively); in 2020 and 2022, a decrease (-5.1% and -38.4%, respectively); the decrease in these revenues in 2023 may amount to 32.0%.

The maximum decrease in revenues from the environmental tax levied on the generation and/or temporary storage of waste occurred in 2022 compared to 2021 (-24.7%); the maximum increase in revenues from the environmental tax levied on the generation and/or temporary storage of waste occurred in 2017 compared to 2016 (+25.6%).

Revenues from the environmental tax on carbon dioxide emissions are characterized by stable growth (+11.7% in 2020; +11.4% in 2021; +38.5% in 2022 and +12.0% in 2023 (forecast) compared to the previous periods).

While analyzing revenues from environmental taxes, it is important to examine the expenditure component as an instrument of a coherent environmental and fiscal policy. Expenditures on environmental protection include all expenditures on preventing, minimizing or eliminating negative effects. Table 1 shows environmental expenditures by type of budget and in total.

Table 1: Environmental protection expenditures in Ukraine.

Year	Local budgets, million UAH		State budget, UAH million		Consolidated budget, million UAH	
	Total, UAH million	Per 1 person, UAH	Total, UAH million	Per 1 person, UAH	Total, UAH million	Per 1 person, UAH
2015	1477	34	4053	95	5530	129
2016	1484	35	4772	112	6255	147
2017	2609	61	4740	112	7349	173
2018	3001	71	5241	124	8242	195
2019	3414	81	6316	151	9730	232
2020	3777	90	7433	178	11211	268
2021	3266	78	9299	223	12565	301

2022	513	14	4714	131	5227	145
2023 (prediction)	760		4437		5195	

Source: systematized according to [16].

In 2015-2021, local environmental expenditures increased by UAH 1789 million (121.1%), while state budget expenditures increased by UAH 5246 million (129.4%). According to the consolidated budget, expenditures increased by UAH 7035 million, which is 127.2%. For a more objective assessment, we analyzed these expenditures per capita, as it is important not only to increase expenditures in general, but to do so in proportion to the population. In 2015-2021, expenditures per capita increased by UAH 172 (+133.3%), including UAH 128 (+134.7%) from the state budget and UAH 44.0 (+129.4%) from local budgets. That is, expenditures per capita are growing at a higher rate than total expenditures.

Let's take a closer look at 2022. Total expenditures on environmental protection decreased by UAH 7338 million (-58.4%) from UAH 12565 million to UAH 5227 million, including UAH 4585 million (-49.3%) from the state budget and UAH 2753 million (-84.3%) from local budgets. Expenditures per capita decreased by UAH 156 (-51.8%): state budget expenditures - by UAH 92 (-41.3%); local budgets - by UAH 64 (-82.1%).

Expenditures as a percentage of GDP according to the local budget in 2015-2021 amounted to 0.1%, and in 2022 the figure decreased. According to the state budget, the value averaged 0.2%, except for 2018 and 2022, when the figure was 0.1%. According to the consolidated budget, this value was 0.3% in 2015-2016 and 2020, and 0.2% in 2017-2019 and 2021; in 2022, the share decreased to 0.1%.

Next, let's analyze environmental expenditures in more detail by functional classification of expenditures. We used the consolidated budget figures for the general and special funds (Table 2).

Table 2: Ukraine's environmental protection expenditures by functional classification, UAH million.

Year	Type of budget	Prevention and elimination of environmental pollution	Preservation of the nature reserve fund	Fundamental and practical research and developments in the field of environmental protection	Other activities in the field of environmental protection
2015	State	3331,5	53,9	81,3	586,2
	Local	963,6	59,5		453,6
	Consolidated	4295,1	113,4	81,3	1039,8
2016	State	4054,8	209,6	84,8	422,5
	Local	1179,8	49,7		254,4
	Consolidated	5234,5	259,3	84,8	676,8
2017	State	3651,1	361,6	104,3	622,8
	Local	1813,6	66,6		729,0

	Consolidated	5464,8	428,3	104,3	1351,9
	State	3660,8	420	130,4	1029,9
2018	Local	1519,4	39,1		1442,2
	Consolidated	5180,2	459,2	130,4	2472,1
	State	4774,1	501,6	197,4	842,9
2019	Local	1559,3	52,3		1801,7
	Consolidated	6333,5	554	197,4	2644,7
	State	5416	549,7	167,5	503,5
2020	Local	1091,9	64,7		1263,1
	Consolidated	6507,9	614,4	167,5	1766,6
	State	6616	837,9	121	625,1
2021	Local	1062,9	100,6		1256,7
	Consolidated	7679	938,6	121	1881,9
	State	3143,8	857,8	202	510,3
2022	Local	184,7	56,4		271,3
	Consolidated	3328,5	914,3	202	781,7
	State	3087,8	782,9	105,1	458,8
2023	Local	184,8	50,5		524,4
(prediction)	Consolidated	3272,6	833,4	105,1	983,3

Source: based on data from [17].

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In 2015-2022, the largest share of environmental protection expenditures was allocated to prevent and eliminate environmental pollution. During 2015-2018, according to the state budget, their share decreased from 82.2% to 69.8%, and during 2018-2022, it increased from 69.8% to 81.6% (+11.8%); further, there is a 14.9% decrease in expenditures (from 81.6% to 66.7%). According to the local budget indicators for 2018-2022, these expenditures decreased by 14.9%. During 2018-2021, in the consolidated budget, expenditures on the prevention and elimination of environmental pollution increased by 9.5%, and in 2022 decreased by 14.0% compared to 2021. The projected calculation for 2023 reflects an increase of 2.9%. The bulk of expenditures were made at the expense of the state budget. During 2018-2021, there was an increase in the consolidated budget of 48.2%, including an increase in the state budget of 80.7% and a decrease in the local budget of 30.0%. In 2022, revenues to local budgets decreased by 82.6%, the state budget by 52.5%, and the consolidated budget by 56.7%.

Expenditures on the conservation of the nature reserves from the state budget in 2015-2020 fluctuate in the range of 1.3-8.3%, increasing to 10.2% (+1.9%) in 2021 and 18.2% (+8.0%) in 2022. These expenditures at the expense of local budgets are characterized by a gradual decrease from 4.0% in 2015 to 1.3% in 2018, and an increase from 1.3% to 11.0% (+9.7%) during 2018-2022. Also during this period, expenditures on the conservation of the nature reserves increased by 104.2% in the state budget; by 44.2% in the local budget and by 99.1% in the consolidated budget. In 2023, the above expenditures are expected to decrease.

Fundamental and practical research and developments in the field of environmental protection is financed exclusively from the state budget and accounts for less than 5.0% in the period 2015-2022.

Expenditures on other environmental protection activities are largely financed from local budgets and account for 30.7-52.2% of total expenditures in this area in 2015-2022. In the structure of state budget expenditures, their share decreased by 5.6% in 2016, then increased by 4.2% in 2017 and 6.6% in 2018 compared to the previous year; then decreased

to 7.6% by 2021, and increased to 10.8% in 2022. According to the consolidated budget, these expenditures increased by 7.0% in 2018-2019. This was due to a 24.9% increase in local expenditures and an 18.2% decrease in state expenditures. In 2020, expenditures decreased by 33.2% in the consolidated budget, and in 2021 they increased by 6.5% compared to the previous period. In 2022, there was a 58.5% reduction in expenditures in general, including 18.4% from the state budget and 78.4% from the local budget. The forecast for 2023 shows an increase in expenditures by 25.8% overall.

To assess the effectiveness of the state's policy in the field of environmental protection, we analyze the dependence of pollutant emissions on the amount of environmental expenditures, investments in this area, and revenues from environmental tax. The atmospheric air and the costs and revenues associated with it were chosen to be the object of this study (Table 3). The reasonableness of this choice is confirmed by the official statistical data of Ukraine. In addition, it is determined that emissions into the atmosphere can be regulated depending on the activities of business entities and the population as a whole.

Table 3: Air pollutant emissions, expenditures and investments in air protection, and environmental tax revenues in Ukraine.

Year	Emissions of major pollutants into the atmosphere, thousand tons (y)	Expenditures on air protection, UAH million (x)1	Investments in air and climate protection, UAH million (x)2	Revenues from the environmental tax levied on air emissions, UAH million (x)3
2015	4521,3	62,7	58,7	48,9
2016	4686,6	62,2	88,5	110,7
2017	4230,6	70,1	86,9	85,4
2018	4121,2	90,2	109,1	80,3
2019	4108,3	102,4	147,7	124,7
2020	3675,3	77,2	181,7	98,9
2021	4521,3	62,7	58,7	48,9

Source: systematized according to [18; 15]. [18; 15].

First of all, we tested the existence of a relationship between the dependent and independent variables (Table 4).

Table 4. Results of the correlation analysis.

	y	x1	x2	x3
y	1			
x1	-0,54587	1		
x2	-0,86366	0,597439	1	
x3	-0,22517	0,501104	0,620521	1

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel.

The Chaddock scale was used to interpret the level of the interdependence. The study showed that there is a high correlation between the performance indicator and x2, a medium correlation between y and x1, and a very close correlation between y and x3. It is worth noting the existence of an inverse relationship between the performance attribute

and all the factor attributes. For further analysis, we selected x2 as the factor that has the greatest impact on air pollutant emissions (-0.86).

Further, based on the regression analysis, the dependence of air pollutant emissions on investments in this area was determined (Table 5).

Table 5. Results of the regression analysis.

Indicator	The value for x2
Multiple R	0,863664
R-square	0,745916
Normalized R-squared	0,682395
Standard error	199,6411
Observations	6

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel

The multiple correlation coefficient shows the total correlation between y and x2 (0.863664) and indicates a strong relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The coefficient of determination shows the overall quality of the model and is 0.745916 and shows that the estimated parameters of the model are 74.6% explained by the dependence between the estimated parameters. The rest (25.4%) are inherent in factors not taken into account in the proposed model. The described indicators confirm the regularity of the studied dependence.

The results of the analysis of variance are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Results of the analysis of variance.

	df	SS	MS	F	The significance of F
Regression	1	468029,2	468029,2	11,74283	0,026614
Balance	4	159426,3	39856,58		
Together	5	627455,5			

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel.

The adequacy of the model is confirmed by the Fisher's criterion. When comparing the observed Fisher's criterion with the tabulated one, it was found that with a reliability coefficient of 0.95 and the significance of the hypothesis of 0.05, the calculated value of F (11.74283) is greater than the tabulated value of 0.026614. And since the significance of F is less than 0.05, it can be argued that the model is adequate according to the Fisher criterion with a reliability level of 0.95.

The existence of a connection within this model is confirmed by the correlation coefficients (Table 7).

Table 7. Table of coefficients

	Ratios	Standard error	t-statistic	P-value	The bottom 95%	The upper 95%
Y-section	4984,504	236,4542	21,08021	2,99E-05	4328,002	5641,006
x1	-6,78489	1,979959	-3,42678	0,026614	-12,2821	-1,28764

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel.

The linear regression equation can be represented as follows:

$$y = b_0 + b_1x_1, \quad (1)$$

From the table, the linear regression coefficients were determined: $b_0 = 4984.504$; $b_1 = -6.78489$. According to the Student's criterion, the coefficient is statistically significant. Based on the linear model, the predicted values in (Table 8) were determined.

Table 8. Projected emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere.

Year	Emissions of major pollutants into the atmosphere, thousand tons (y)	Investments in air and climate protection, UAH million (x2)	Emissions of major pollutants into the atmosphere, thousand tons (predicted value)
2015	4521,3	58,7	4586,0
2016	4686,6	88,5	4384,3
2017	4230,6	86,9	4394,8
2018	4121,2	109,1	4244,5
2019	4108,3	147,7	3982,2
2020	3675,3	181,7	3751,5

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel according to [18; 15]. .

The scatter of values on the normal distribution graph is small, which confirms the accuracy of the model (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Graph of normal distribution.

Source: built using Microsoft Excel

The study found that emissions of pollutants into the air are inversely proportional to investments in this area: the higher the amount of investment, the lower the emissions.

As Ukraine aspires to become a member of the European Union, we believe it is appropriate to conduct a similar analysis of the performance of individual EU member states. Poland and Romania, which are Ukraine's neighbors and cooperate with our country, were chosen for this stage of the study. In addition, these countries are characterized by different levels of economic and social development, which allows us to assess environmental policy in the presence of disproportionate environmental opportunities.

The data for the analysis of Poland's indicators are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Air pollutant emissions, expenditures, investments in air protection, and revenues from pollution taxes in Poland

Year	Emissions of major pollutants into the atmosphere, thousand tons (y)	Expenditures on environmental protection, EUR million (x)1	Investments in air protection and climate protection, EUR million (x)2	Revenues from pollution taxes, EUR million (x)3
2015	340984,2	1629,2	112,2	725,13
2016	352343,1	1306,5	51,5	594,98
2017	368592,5	1350,9	50,9	559,08
2018	367225,1	1645,1	145,1	538,54
2019	350689	1652	207,1	572,65
2020	334791,2	1262,1	167,7	663,08

Source: systematized according to [19]

At the first stage, as in the analysis of Ukraine's indicators, we checked the interconnection between the dependent and independent variables (Table 10).

Table 10. Results of the correlation analysis. Таблица 10.

	y	x1	x2	x3
y	1			
x1	0,174418	1		
x2	-0,38216	0,483731	1	
x3	-0,83934	-0,05232	0,051072	1

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel.

Based on the Chaddock scale, the following was found. There is a weak inverse relationship between the performance attribute and factor x1 ; between y and x2 - a moderate inverse relationship; between y and x3 - a high inverse relationship. Further analysis will be based on the indicators of the factor x3 .

The next step is to conduct a regression analysis (Table 11).

Table 11. Results of the regression analysis

Indicator.	The value for x3
Multiple R	0,83934206
R-square	0,704495095
Normalized R-squared	0,630618868
Standard error	8267,839883
Observations.	6

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel.

The multiple correlation coefficient proves the existence of a strong relationship between the outcome and factor attributes. The coefficient of determination (R-square) shows that the model parameters are 70.4% explained by the dependence of y and x3. The determined indicators confirm the regularity of the studied dependence.

The results of the analysis of variance are shown in Table 12.

Table 12. Results of the analysis of variance.

	df	SS	MS	F	The significance of F
Regression	1	651864581,6	651864581,6	9,53615431	0,036643091
Balance	4	273428705,3	68357176,33		
Together	5	925293286,9			

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel.

The analysis of the Fisher's criterion showed that the significance of F 0.036643091 0.05, which confirms the adequacy of the model. It should also be noted that, according to this criterion, the calculated value with a model reliability level of 95% is higher than the tabulated value.

The correlation coefficients are presented in Table 13.

Table 13. Table of coefficients.

	Ratios	Standard error	t-statistic	P-value	The bottom 95%	The upper 95%
Y-section	450013,033	31777,3782	14,1614274	0,00014435	361784,89	538241,179
x_1	-160,2462	51,89208442	-3,08806644	0,03664309	-304,3217	-16,170680

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel..

The following linear regression coefficients were obtained: $b_0 = 450013.033$; $b_1 = -160.2462$. The test by the Student's criterion showed the statistical significance of b_0 , b_1 .

The calculated values of pollutant emissions are shown in Table 14..

Table 14. Projected emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere.

Year	Emissions of major pollutants into the atmosphere, thousand tons (y)	Revenues from pollution taxes, EUR million (x)3	Emissions of major pollutants into the atmosphere, thousand tons (predicted value)
2015	4521,3	58,7	4586,0
2016	4686,6	88,5	4384,3
2017	4230,6	86,9	4394,8
2018	4121,2	109,1	4244,5
2019	4108,3	147,7	3982,2
2020	3675,3	181,7	3751,5

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel according to [19].

The accuracy of the model is confirmed by a normal distribution graph with a small spread of values (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Graph of the normal distribution.

Source: built using Microsoft Excel

Romania was chosen as another country for comparative analysis. The initial information for the calculations is presented in Table 15.

Table 15. Air pollutant emissions, expenditures, investments in air protection, and revenues from pollution taxes in Romania.

Year	Emissions of major pollutants into the atmosphere, thousand tons (y)	Expenditures on environmental protection, EUR million (x)1	Investments in air protection and climate protection, EUR million (x)2	Revenues from pollution taxes, EUR million (x)3
2015	104264,8	1111,2	104,6	8,21
2016	100113,4	1261,2	18,3	10,47
2017	102233,3	1220,4	6,9	9,78
2018	102372,8	1255,9	4,7	9,45
2019	98747,1	1688,3	4,9	8,85
2020	94137,7	1823,2	6,2	9,14

Source: systematized according to [19].

The results of the correlation analysis for Romania are shown in Table 16

Table 16. Results of the correlation analysis.

	y	x1	x2	x3
y	1			
x1	-0,931071536	1		
x2	0,544238461	-0,517229923	1	
x3	-0,115870636	-0,135166097	-0,609250925	1

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel.

According to the Chaddock scale, there is a close relationship with factor x1 ; a significant relationship with factor x2 , and a weak relationship with factor x3 . Also, the correlation analysis showed a direct relationship with factor x2 and an inverse relationship with factors x1 and x3 . For the regression analysis, factor x1 was chosen, which has the greatest impact on y. The results are presented in Table 17.

Table 17. Results of the regression analysis.

Indicator.	The value for x1
Multiple R	0,931071536
R-square	0,866894204
Normalized R-squared	0,833617755
Standard error	1461,320607
Observations	6

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel.

The total correlation between y and x1 according to the correlation coefficient is 0.931071536 and confirms the existence of a strong relationship between the variables. According to the R-squared data, it was determined that the estimated model parameters are 86.7% explained by the outcome and factor attributes; 13.3% are accounted for by other factors.

The next step is to conduct an analysis of variance (Table 18).

Table 18. Results of the analysis of variance.

	df	SS	MS	F	Значущість F
Regression	1	55631419,56	55631419,56	26,0512835	0,006962956
Balance	4	8541831,664	2135457,916		
Together	5	64173251,23			

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel

Comparison of Fisher's criterion by calculated and tabulated values showed that the model is adequate, since $26.0512835 > 0.006962956$ and $0.006962956 < 0.05$ with a reliability coefficient of 95% and a hypothesis significance of 5%.

The calculated correlation coefficients are shown in Table 19.

Table 19: Table of coefficients.

	Ratios	Standard error	t-statistic	P-value	The bottom 95%	The upper 95%
Y-section	116392,9	3206,693	36,29686	3,44E-06	107489,7	125296,1
x1	-11,5414	2,261221	-5,10405	0,006963	-17,8195	-5,26322

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel

The following linear regression coefficients were obtained: $b_0 = 116392.9$; $b_1 = -11.5414$. The Student's criterion confirmed the statistical significance of the coefficients.

Based on the linear model, the predicted values in (Table 20) were determined.

Table 20. Projected emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere.

Year	Emissions of major pollutants into the atmosphere, thousand tons (y)	Expenditures on environmental protection, EUR million (x)3	Emissions of major pollutants into the atmosphere, thousand tons (Predicted value)
2015	104264,8	1111,2	103568,1
2016	100113,4	1261,2	101836,9
2017	102233,3	1220,4	102307,8
2018	102372,8	1255,9	101898,1

2019	98747,1	1688,3	96907,6
2020	94137,7	1823,2	95350,6

Source: calculated using Microsoft Excel according to [19].

The small scatter of values on the normal distribution graph proves the accuracy of the model (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Graph of normal distribution.

Source: built using Microsoft Excel

4. Discussion

To ensure sustainable development, it is necessary to maintain a rational balance between the resources used by humanity and the problems that arise in the process of their use. Therefore, it is important to find ways to compensate for the damage caused. The need for greater efficiency of environmental measures and increased sources of their financing indicates the insufficient stability of the environment [3].

The use of various economic and legal instruments in the field of regulation of environmental relations is inextricably linked to environmental management, the success and effectiveness of which is determined by the effectiveness of measures to protect the environment and preserve natural resources and ecosystems [20]. In modern conditions, it is important to achieve effective coherence and cooperation of all institutions responsible for the management and coordination of measures for the protection and rational use of natural resources of Ukraine. [21]. The role of public environmental management is crucial in addressing the complex problems caused by human activity and climate change. However, global instability complicates the effective conduct of environmental management[22].

Understanding the various sources and instruments of financing for adaptational measures based on an ecosystemic and nature-oriented approach will contribute not only to the creation of an effective and balanced portfolio of climate finance for climate change adaptation, but also to the development of a new method of forming a national budget aimed at mitigating and adapting to climate change [23].

5. Conclusions

The main challenges in the field of environmental finance are insufficient funding, limited financial resources, and changes in the ratio of environmental tax distribution, which lead to low efficiency of using funds for environmental protection measures [5].

The ability of Ukraine to provide financial support for the implementation of the environmental management strategy will largely depend on what steps can be taken within the existing organizational and legal structure for financing environmental activities. Therefore, understanding this structure is an important step in developing the

necessary economic mechanisms to support and implement a strategy for the rational use of natural resources [24].

Ensuring a balanced ecological and economic development at different levels of economic activity is possible through achieving economic efficiency in financing environmental protection measures. In particular, the introduction of a methodology for assessing the effectiveness of air purification measures at the level of enterprise will allow to evaluate and balance costs and benefits [25].

The correlation and regression analysis has shown that Ukraine's financial and environmental policy is not effective enough. This is due to the irrational interrelation of pollutant emissions and the funds invested in this area and the solution of these problems. Based on the study, it was found that the obtained models are adequate and can be used to build future predictions of pollutant emissions.

Based on the results of the analysis, taking into account the situation in Ukraine after the beginning of the full-scale Russian invasion and the trends in the EU countries, the following directions for the development of financial and environmental policy are proposed:

- The post-war restoration of the environmental situation should be carried out on the basis of sustainable development, focusing on the European Green Deal;
- Implementation of the triple objective: environmental restoration, minimization of negative climate change and balanced use of resources;
- Expanding the powers of the relevant ministry with a focus on the strategic goals of state policy in this area in order to strengthen cooperation with international institutions in solving environmental problems;
- methodological recommendations should be developed in accordance with international standards for assessing the real state of the environment coupled with its financial interpretation;
- A fundamental reform of the system of allocating funds for environmental purposes should be carried out by means of identifying specific priority areas and setting clear restrictions on the direction of funds;
- state and local budgets should provide funds for environmental protection measures based on the real needs of each individual region.

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